

Performance Evaluation and Data Transfer Improvements for Planck-LFI Data Analysis

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Abstract

Planck is a mission of the European Space Agency (ESA) to map the anisotropies of the cosmic microwave background with the highest accuracy ever achieved. Planck is supported by several computing centres, including CSC (Finland) and NERSC (USA). Computational resources were provided by CSC through the DECI project Planck-LFI, and by NERSC as a regular production project. This whitepaper describes how PRACE-2IP staff helped Planck-LFI with two types of support tasks: (1) porting their applications to the execution machine and seeking ways to improve applications' performance; and (2) improving performance and facilities to transfer data between the execution site and the different data centres where data is stored.

Introduction

Application support is a service activity of the PRACE-2IP project. It provides dedicated support for research projects that have been granted access to HPC resources through DECI (Distributed European Computing Initiative). The support can be given by a local expert who is specialised in the type of the PRACE Tier-1 platform the project has been given access to, an expert who is already in close contact to the project members, or an expert who has special skills in particular support activities. The support may include porting an application to a new platform, improving application's performance, and so forth. The work typically lasts 0–1 months, but there are projects that received a lot more support. One of those projects is Planck-LFI.

PRACE-2IP staff helped Planck-LFI in two types of support tasks: (1) porting their applications on the execution machine and seeking ways to improve applications' performance; and (2) improving performance and facilities to transfer data between the execution site and the different datacentres where data is stored. The work done was essential for the project's success.

DECI project Planck-LFI

Planck is a satellite mission of the European Space Agency (ESA) to map the structure of the cosmic microwave background. The accuracy, sensitivity, and angular resolution of Planck are superior to the earlier missions (COBE in the 1990s and WMAP in the 2000s). The cosmic microwave background is radiation from the Big Bang, and it shows us the structure of the early universe. Planck constrains cosmological models and examines the birth of large-scale structure in the universe. The main scientific results from Planck are cosmological, but as a by-product, Planck also produces all-sky maps of all the major sources of microwave to far-infrared emission, opening a broad expanse of other astrophysical topics to be investigated.

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The Planck satellite was launched in May 2009. The first cosmological results will be published in early 2013; there will be a second release in early 2014; and probably a final third release with the final results from the mission in 2015. An example of the early results is shown in Fig. 1.

Planck carries two instruments, the Low-Frequency Instrument (LFI) and the High-Frequency Instrument (HFI). Two Planck data processing centres were set up, one for each instrument, but the most resource-intensive tasks need to be done on supercomputers. Some parts of the Planck LFI data analysis are computationally too heavy to run at the LFI data processing centre. For example, map-making (including removal of correlated noise) involves correlations in the data over all time scales, leading to a massively parallel computational problem requiring a lot of communication between different processes. This is 10–20 times faster on the Cray XT supercomputer at CSC (Finland) than at the LFI data processing centre. An important step of the data analysis was to repeat it hundreds or thousands of times for different realizations of simulated data that matched the properties of the flight data.

Computational resources for this work were provided by CSC through the DECI project Planck-LFI, and by NERSC (USA) as a regular production project. Application support was received from these sites and PRACE-2IP. The reason for submitting a DECI proposal and not just using the systems at NERSC – which are of the same type and bigger – was that it was not considered a satisfactory situation that a major European project would depend on American resources that were allocated on a year-by-year basis by an American agency (DOE). Dividing the work between European and American computing centres made this a European–American collaborative effort with a more reasonable division in contribution of resources, and a larger total amount of resources. Working in collaboration required that the data had to be gathered in one place (often NERSC). This raised a need for a fast data connection between CSC and NERSC.

Fig. 1. (a) The Planck satellite. (b) “Galactic haze” above and below the Milky Way. (Parts where other kinds of radiation are too strong for a reliable separation of the haze component are shown in black.) Images: ESA/Planck

Application support

Planck-LFI used many different applications and transferred a lot of data between different storage locations (especially CSC and NERSC), which also increased the need for support.

There were three things that required a larger amount of support. The first was the need for a fast data transfer connection between CSC and NERSC, to compare and combine results. Improvements in this area made by PRACE-2IP are described in the “data transfer improvements” section.

The second support task was the insufficient parallel scalability of the Madam map-making application in some situations. The main reason for bad performance in these situations is the use of all-to-all communications, which cannot be changed. However, any improvement to the application would be useful. To identify performance bottlenecks, the application was profiled with the CrayPat performance analysis tool. The tool revealed that the performance is degraded because sending MPI processes have more work to do than the receiving ones. However, this didn’t result in suggestions to optimize the code.

The third support task was porting of the Planck likelihood code to the Cray XT system. Application support staff assisted in this task.

Data transfer improvements

Planck-LFI transferred hundreds of gigabytes of data per week between CSC and NERSC, and hence any improvements made in the data transfer connections or software were useful to them. Partly due to these kinds of demands, a new tool, named gtransfer, for data transfers was developed at HLRS^a with testing by CSC starting already in the DEISA-2 project (RI-222919). Gtransfer is now available to users as an additional service in PRACE-2IP. Planck-LFI was a pilot project to test out the feasibility of the tool. It was an immediate success. By increasing transfer rates (by a factor of 25 compared to scp, see Fig. 1), gtransfer enabled larger amounts of data to be transferred in a shorter time.

Gtransfer^{b,c} provides an advanced interface for GridFTP transfers, which enables data movement along predefined paths by using transit sites. In addition data movement is optimized by applying special settings for specific network connections, based on the information that has been provided by PRACE-2IP staff in advance. Alternatively the latest version of gtransfer can also apply special settings depending on the file size. For example special optimizations – like increased concurrency, which means that many files can be transferred at the same time – are used. This improves data transfer performance for small files (< 50 MB) considerably. Gtransfer also supports reliable data transfers, which means that failed transfers will be retried. And if needed, data transfers can also be interrupted by a user and continued later on from where they were interrupted.

Therefore gtransfer can ease the data transfer tasks of users in several ways. Usage is made easy so users just have to provide the source and the destination of a transfer and gtransfer will take care of the rest, provided that the user has the authorisation to access both sites. Gtransfer can even help users by specifying their source/destination files and directories by completing remote paths directly on the command line. This way users can traverse remote directory structures from where they are working; there is no need to determine the correct paths with another tool (like SSH) prior to a transfer.

Fig. 2. Instead of using a direct but slow connection (dashed red line; bandwidth: 1 Gb/s) between CSC and NERSC, gtransfer (gt) reroutes the data transfer through SURF SARA (yellow lines; bandwidth: (1) 10 Gb/s (dedicated), (2) 10 Gb/s (shared)) and achieves a higher performance that way.

^a Leader GridFTP subtask (DEISA2), Leader Data Subtask (PRACE-1IP,2IP,3IP)
^b <http://bit.ly/gtransfer-demo>
^c <http://bit.ly/gtransfer>

The Internet connection of CSC's Cray XT is limited to 1 Gigabit/s. The connection to other PRACE sites is much faster: 10 Gigabit/s. The 10 Gigabit/s connectivity is in use also in the official gateways of PRACE and NERSC. Therefore without gtransfer Planck-LFI users needed to reroute data through these official gateways in order to get a good performance. That meant that the user first had to copy his data to one of these gateways and in another step from there to the destination. This included waiting for the first transfer to finish before starting the second one, and not to forget to use all options that improve performance, which is especially important on public shared networks. With gtransfer, everything is automated. The user only has to specify the source and destination of a transfer.

Fig. 2 shows that the transfer rate was 25 times higher with gtransfer than it was with SSH.

Summary

PRACE-2IP staff helped Planck-LFI in two types of support tasks: (1) porting their applications on the execution machine and seeking ways to improve applications' performance; and (2) improving performance and facilities to transfer data between the execution site and the other places where data is stored. The work done was essential for the project's success.

The LFI instrument of Planck is still in operation and will gather data until August 2013. The work will continue within a follow-up DECI project, named Planck-LFI2, preparing for the second Planck data release and publication of cosmological results, which takes place in early 2014. Porting support and gtransfer development will be continued to aid that project.

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